

Table continued

Variety	IRRI acc. no.	Country of origin	Reaction ^a to races			
			1 (PXO 61)	2 (PXO 86)	3 (PXO 79)	4 (Pxo 71)
Sajani	16177	Nepal	R	R	R	S
Sokan Dhan	16250	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Tally	16146	Nepal	R	R	R	MR
Gokhue Sair	16195	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Mujaer	18296	Indonesia	R	R	R	MS
DL 5	8593	Pakistan	R	R	R	MS

^a R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

have an additional gene for resistance.

A vast majority of the varieties came from gene center 1, comprising Bangladesh, Nepal, and northeast India. One variety is from Indonesia and one from Pakistan. □

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Reaction of IR varieties to tungro (RTV) in the Philippines

E.R. Tiongco, R.C. Cabunagan, Z.M. Flores, and H. Hibino, Plant Pathology Department; and O. Garcia, R. Necesario, and G.L. Denning, Training and Technology Transfer Department, IRRI

IR varieties were tested for reaction to RTV during the 1986 dry season in Koronadal, South Cotabato; Baybay, Leyte; and Guimba, Nueva Ecija. Disease incidence was based on symptoms; rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) in rice plants were indexed by the latex test 60 d after transplanting. Symptoms of RTV incidence in fields surrounding the test sites were assessed visually.

RTV incidence varied among varieties and locations (see table). In Nueva Ecija, where virtually no RTV incidence

was observed in the surrounding fields, only RTSV infection occurred in all varieties. In Leyte, where RTV incidence was moderately low, high levels of RTSV infection and low levels of RTBV infection occurred in all varieties. In South Cotabato, where RTV incidence was high, many varieties were infected with both viruses.

Even under high disease pressure in South Cotabato, IR56, IR60, and IR62 had relatively low infection rates. IR50, IR54, and IR64, which have Gam Pai 30-12-15 as a donor for vector resistance in their parentage, showed low infection rates with either virus in Nueva Ecija but high infection rates in Leyte and South Cotabato. IR26 and IR30 were mostly infected with RTBV alone in South Cotabato.

These results indicate field resistance to RTV in IR50, IR54, and IR64 in Nueva Ecija but not in Leyte and South Cotabato.

The latex test on test plants and plants from surrounding fields in South Cotabato revealed 12% infection with rice grassy stunt virus (GSV). It seemed that GSV strain 2, which caused RTV-like symptoms, was prevalent in South Cotabato. GSV-infected plants might have been scored RTV-infected.

These results confirm that RTV incidence varies with disease severity and the vector population prevailing in the area. Unsuspected RTSV occurs widely in fields perceived to be disease-free. □

Ketoacids in healthy and bacterial blight (BB)-affected leaves of susceptible and tolerant rice varieties

Ch. Ramanamma and A. Sreeramulu, Botany Department, S. V. University, Tirupati 517502, A. P., India

Ketoacids act as precursors of amino acids. Their alteration may affect the composition of amino acids during disease development in rice leaves.

Three ketoacids — pyruvic acid, α -ketoglutaric acid, and an unknown ketoacid — were detected in healthy and inoculated plants of susceptible TN1 and tolerant IET4141 rice varieties. Their content during disease development in inoculated leaves of both varieties was greater than in healthy leaves. Disease stages 1 to 5 were monitored at 2, 5, 10, 15, and 20 d after inoculation of 55-d-old rice plants with a virulent isolate of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*.

RTV incidence based on symptoms, and RTBV and RTSV infection based on the latex test in IR varieties 60 d after transplanting in fields in Nueva Ecija, Leyte, and South Cotabato, Philippines.

Variety	Nueva Ecija ^a		Leyte			South Cotabato			
	RTSV infection (%)	RTV incidence (%)	Infection (%)			RTV incidence (%)	Infection (%)		
			RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV	RTSV		RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
IR22	11	61	20	13	11	99	50	8	29
IR26	12	0	0	2	0	89	0	34	0
IR30	10	0	0	1	0	49	2	37	1
IR36	29	5	4	3	22	92	19	12	19
IR42	26	25	17	4	64	98	25	14	20
IR50	9	1	2	2	28	100	39	10	19
IR54	4	3	4	2	48	100	65	5	21
IR56	5	0	0	1	2	5	1	2	10
IR60	26	0	0	1	4	29	1	3	11
IR62	13	0	0	0	4	7	4	2	25
IR64	6	3	2	2	28	100	31	15	22

^a No visual scoring made. No RTBV+RTSV or RTBV infection observed.